

Modern Views on Teaching English in the Professional Development of Veterinary Students

Kenjabayev Shakir Abdulkhalimovich

Samarkand state veterinary medicine, livestock and biotechnology university Tashkent Branch

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the determination of effective strategies for teaching English, and the purpose of our research is to study the methods of improving the professional skills of veterinary medicine students based on the English language. In the article, the use of factors that are used and influence the improvement of English language teaching in the development of professional competences of veterinary students in the educational process, and the issues related to the extent to which they can be interested in the lesson and gain knowledge in order for the lessons to have an effective result. 'considered.

Keywords: Veterinary terminology, innovative technology, approach, traditional method, modern method, pedotechnologies, competence, information communication technologies, continuous education, academic, speech competence, contextual, tool, didactics, program, computer, electronic communication, process, system, project, opportunity.

At a time when the scientific potential of our country's scientists is growing, international relations with various countries are expanding, and cooperation with them is strengthening and developing, this issue is gaining special importance in the field of education. Based on this, we teach English as a compulsory part of secondary and higher education. In today's world, the need for large-scale use of information and information, arising as a result of globalization, has increased the need to learn foreign languages and develop communicative competence of specialists in all fields. In world practice, special attention is paid to conducting scientific research on the use of an integrative approach to language education, integrative curricula and textbooks in the development of communicative competence in foreign languages..

The organization of modern education in the process of learning English, the introduction of effective methodological methods to this process, increasing the need for independent education of the student in learning English, the problems of satisfying it and their solution are one of the most urgent problems of today. is appearing. In this regard, the unique features of teaching English, the scientific-theoretical pedagogical foundations of improving new teaching technologies have been revealed.

Teaching foreign languages to the youth of the country is one of the urgent tasks of the reforms implemented in the field of education. Teaching English and learning this language on a large scale means owning this language as a leading communication tool in world science, economy, and culture. From this point of view, it is important to use modern

educational methods in teaching this language. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2016 "Procurement of foreign educational and scientific literature for the higher education system" "On measures for the further development of the higher education system" No. VMQ-174 dated April 20, 2017 No. PQ-2909 dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-4306, dated August 27, 2021, dated May 3, 2019, "On measures to identify talented young people and create a continuous education system for training highly qualified personnel VMQ-546, dated January 19, 2022, "On measures to establish the Foreign Languages TV and radio channel" VMQ-34, dated January 19, 2022, "On additional measures to improve the study of foreign languages" - VMQ-513 of September "On measures to support non-governmental educational organizations for the organization of foreign language teaching activities in rural areas", "IT- In accordance with the decree and decisions No. PQ-178 on the organization of the activities of "towns", the decisions of November 29, 2023 "On amendments and additions to the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on veterinary medicine" Organizational measures for the popularization of language learning are being carried out effectively. Introduction of digital technologies and modern teaching methods to higher education processes in the "Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019, practical training in specialized subjects aimed at broad involvement in scientific activities, fighting corruption, increasing the share of students studying in engineering and technical education, introducing a credit-module system, increasing practical skills in curricula specific tasks for increasing the share of training have been defined. Also, life itself requires the implementation of reforms in all areas of our country, changing people's worldview, training mature and up-to-date specialists. In the republic, great importance is attached to strengthening the education system and harmonizing it with the requirements of the times. In this regard, it is important that the system of training, education and upbringing of specialist personnel is closely connected with the demands of reforms. Training of specialist personnel who can meet the requirements of the time, improvement of education and all its structural structures based on the requirements of the State is one of the urgent issues before us. In this program, credit education systems in foreign countries, innovative methods of organizing educational processes based on the credit system and ensuring its quality, activities of pedagogues in the credit-module system, methodological support of the educational process in the credit-module system, training legal documents related to the field of education and their content, the legal and moral-educational foundations of preventing and fighting corruption in educational institutions, and the normative legal foundations of higher education are described. Today, higher education institutions use normative documents such as the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Education", decrees, decisions and orders in the organization of education and training processes. But until now, the theoretical and practical aspects of the practical application of these documents by subjects of education and training processes have not been studied. These cases indicate the urgency of studying and analyzing the normative and legal frameworks of higher education used in higher education institutions from a comprehensive theoretical and practical point of view. The formation of knowledge and science directly goes back to the education system. The effectiveness of the educational system is directly ensured by the level of the teacher, the needs of students, the content of educational literature, and the infrastructure aimed at the formation of independent education. Therefore, the training of advanced personnel, increasing their competitiveness in accordance with the requirements of

the labor market, and the cultivation of creatively thinking specialists are closely related to the educational process established in educational institutions. The development of general descriptive education is currently associated with the influence of a number of socio-cultural factors (globalization, informationization, digitalization, etc.), which makes the search for ways to expand its potential more urgent. Today, the factors of the competence approach in teaching English in the field of veterinary science, the following directions are of decisive importance in the methodology of teaching compulsory specialty subjects: - "Competency approach model in English language teaching and its content and essence" model to form and develop students' creative ability to dynamic changes, create object models in various data flows, develop new types and forms with language skills; Brief description: the ability to apply acquired knowledge and skills in solving practical pedagogical issues and in unfamiliar situations (competencies).

These standards also consist of practical application standards of a generalized content, which cover the following areas of mental activity of students:

- reasoning - providing logical and understandable arguments to justify, prove, or respond to the opinions of others in English;
- modeling - use of modular assignments to express problems in text, speech, dialogue and monologue forms, build their model;
- solving a problem - solving a problem using specialist terms in English;
- to communicate - to communicate in the translated language based on the concepts, signs and symbols of the specialty;
- working with data - collecting, analyzing and presenting information related to the specialty in various forms.
- spatial imagination - focusing on the development of a culture of free thinking, communication, behavior and activities of students;
- to strengthen the practical component related to situations, to apply knowledge and skills outside the framework of educational situations and to help develop students' functional literacy;

During the course of English language classes in the field of veterinary medicine, students can expand the content of their activities, interact with the geographical space, and create more opportunities for their future life.

Education is defined as "personal and socially significant activity specially organized to familiarize students with descriptive culture - a type of social culture related to knowledge, development and change of geospace.

"The content of the research model shows that the active side of a person's descriptive culture is determined by his professional training experience, which leads to a connection with functional professional literacy.

Each student's self-introduction, identification of interests, development of abilities is directly related to the culture of free thinking in them. Of course, in this, it is important for every teacher to develop the skills of independent and creative thinking in his students, to express their thoughts fluently in writing and verbally, to be critical of themselves in various situations and to critically evaluate the situation, to determine the truth and to strive for it. .

Intended audience and purpose:

This module is designed for a diverse audience, including adult English language teachers, assessors, curriculum and resource developers, test makers, and education professionals.

Currently, this standard sets several key objectives for students, teachers and assessors, as well as the general public.

For teachers: This standard serves as a basis for teachers in planning language teaching and organizing lessons and activities, as well as creating lesson plans.

For students: this standard provides a framework for students to plan their language learning, set goals or adapt, and monitor progress. As a national standard describing communicative language ability, this program can facilitate students' understanding of information, allowing seamless transitions between classes, programs, and institutions.

For evaluators: to what extent does this document teach foreign language learners listening, reading, writing, speaking, and integrated skills based on 21st century skills? can be the basis for checking their possession. Based on the developed requirements, it determines the level of foreign language knowledge of students (A1, A2, A2+, B1 or B1+).

For curriculum and resource developers: this document helps students plan language learning, set goals or adapt and monitor progress, 21st century skills in listening, reading, writing (writing), speaking (speaking) and their integration (integrated skills) will be a guide in the creation of educational materials that will help in the development of the skills listed above.

For test makers: it is possible to create test sets that help to determine the level of language knowledge of students based on the skills ("can do statements") presented in this standard, to guide the correct acquisition of these skills through the created tests gives In the development of professional competences of students in the field of veterinary medicine, the formation of the culture of thinking of students in the teaching of the English language. In the process of English language education, modern types of lessons are comprehensive and are aimed at developing the thoughts of each student about knowledge in relation to the content and form. Today, it is implemented as a set of methods that teach how to independently meet the educational needs of a student. In the lesson, the main focus is on the activity of the teacher to the activity of the student, (on their educational process), that is, the teacher does not start and finish the lesson himself, but shows the student the way to get knowledge, in achieving it must be a partner.

The requirements for the modern lesson are: educational, psychological, hygienic, didactic requirements, which are interrelated and organically implemented. In the didactic requirements for English language classes in the development of professional competences of veterinary students, students should have independent thinking, moral qualities, the ability to connect the knowledge they have received with life, respect for the Motherland, its history, culture, traditions, and most importantly, respect for people. should aim to form a scientific outlook, aesthetic taste, economic, legal, and professional culture.

In terms of psychological requirements for the lesson, knowing the individual-psychological characteristics of students (personal-spiritual), they should have memory, conscious perception, strong will, the ability to imagine, think about abstract phenomena, and acquire knowledge specific to age characteristics on the basis of state education standards. consists of

The process of training specialists in the field of veterinary medicine takes into account the hygienic requirements of the training, the temperature of the air in the auditorium, its cleanliness, and the aesthetic taste. Didactic requirements in teaching English in the development of professional competences of veterinary students include the most important educational components. That is, clearly defining the educational goal of the lesson (forecasting is our opinion), enriching the lesson with life and scientific facts for an interesting organization, achieving mastery of the lessons based on creating a free environment and conditions for students to learn, to go from simple to complex in the narrative part, to be able

to choose the methods and methods suitable for the content of the lesson, to choose suitable educational tools, to ensure the connection of the lesson with other subjects, to achieve objectivity in the assessment of student knowledge, etc. The basis for the development of professional competences of veterinary students is the formation of a culture of free thinking in English classes. In this:

- expansion of students' scope of knowledge and thinking and worldview;
- to acquire knowledge and increase interest in science by critically analyzing, synthesizing, summarizing, applying and evaluating students in working with foreign literature such as scientific, scientific and popular treatises, texts (by creating cognitive motivation);
- being able to apply acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in a new situation;
- education of desire for new knowledge;
- development of self-work skills.

In the development of professional competences of students in the field of veterinary medicine, the importance of problematic and controversial lessons in the explanatory formation of specialist terms in English language teaching is important. For this, the teacher needs students to actively prepare for classes, mutual cooperation and support between them, full expression of their opinions, logical argument, objectivity, listening to the opinions of others patiently and diligently. It is necessary to organize and manage the formation of skills.

Also, the use of various innovative technologies in the development of the professional competences of students in the field of veterinary medicine, in the teaching of English, in the development of the cognitive activity of the teacher occupies a key place in the development and protection of the intellectual creative potential of the students. In this case, the teacher should carry out pedagogical, organizational-methodical work and learn the mechanism of working with talented students and young people, the features of the educational process, their independent activities and develop suggestions for their improvement, methodically evaluate each training session. is the basis of provision. Because the use of an improved pedagogical or psychological method shows its effectiveness. The formation of a culture of free thinking among students in English classes requires a special approach to the educational process. Because in it, the formation of the student's personality - the creation of technologies for inculcating moral norms, spiritual and educational values accepted in the society - serves to ensure positive results. It is known that the subjects of the curriculum of higher education institutions, consisting of a set of compulsory and elective subjects, are the main influencing factor on the thinking process.

Among the psychologists V.M. Karimova, R.I. Sunnatova, R.N. Tajiboevas conditionally divide subjects of science that affect the formation of human thinking into two groups.

Of these:

The first are the subjects that form direct movement skills and abilities (physical education, painting, writing, music, etc.).

The second is more abstract subjects (geography, history, literature, physics, mathematics, etc.) that make you think and understand with imagination. In the first group of subjects, the student learns to behave boldly, gracefully, and intelligently in order to think independently. However, the subjects of the second group are complex for students, and these subjects allow thinking, reasoning logically, understanding abstraction, and understanding the essence of things and events that are not actually in front of the student's eyes. Taking this into account, from the lessons included in the second group, the concept of "practical acquisition of a foreign language", "linguistics", "Learning foreign languages" and the following should be

paid attention to in order to increase the effectiveness of training courses:

- in the organization of English lessons based on the national curriculum Define It, Drawing Distance (Playful Pictures), Run to the Board, Memory Story, Board Race, Pictionary, Lip Reading, Opinion/Running Distances, Word by Word Story, Sleep and Wake Up, the idea of using exercises and the main ideas of reasoning, modeling, problem solving, communication, working with information based on the dialectical laws of dependence on student thinking were perceived by the teacher from a scientific and methodological point of view to ensure the approach without;
- attach importance to the development of the culture of free thinking in the content of lesson topics;
- to study the scientific and literary heritage of Central Asian thinkers during the lesson and to pay attention to their importance in the education of young people;
- development of methods of developing free thinking in the organization of students' independent work during extracurricular activities;
- taking into account the principles of interdisciplinary integration in the organization of classes;
- achieving the creation of a social environment that is an effective factor for students to think freely;
- determining the position of the factors of the working curriculum of subjects based on the requirements set for the purpose of the subject;
- creation of a methodological series of educational and educational activities that contribute to the development of debate culture, reasoning, free observation skills in students to debate and thereby determine the reality of life, the essence of certain problems;
- to establish the use of pedagogical and psychological literature by teachers, which serves to teach students how to overcome fear in boldly expressing their opinions;
- permanent training of teaching personnel in the educational institution aimed at achieving the goal set by the subject with the participation of the methodical department of the educational institution, deputy directors for spirituality and enlightenment, and subject teachers organizing internal employee seminars;
- "Who reads a lot of books?", encouraging students' interest in reading artistic and scientific works when using information-resource centers and libraries. to organize contests within the framework of the educational institution;
- achieving the implementation of the slogan "We think freely, we study freely, we live freely" in the educational institution in the educational process of all subjects;
- thinkers, poets, enlighteners who made a great contribution to the independence and development of our country, who became bright examples of free thinking, who did not lose their selflessness and courage even in the most difficult situations, who sacrificed their lives for their people and homeland, especially paying great attention to the study of the works of individuals who left an indelible mark in our history as representatives of the Jadidist movement at the beginning of the last century.

In order to provide practical help to teachers in forming a culture of free thinking in students, we have developed a special course program and lesson plans, methodological recommendations (Appendix 1). They show the topics, didactic and methodological tools, special topics for subjects, effective organization of lessons and their results aimed at ensuring

the formation of a culture of free thinking in students.

In the "Latin in English" and "English grammar for students of Latin" educational programs, students are taught the content of the textbook at the level of modern requirements and, through practical training, the students' skills and abilities to live in compliance with the law are formed, as well as the students' ability to live according to the law the main attention is focused on the need to study and read their documents independently.

In the course of using the textbooks "Latin in English", "English grammar for students of Latin", students are taught the rules of English language knowledge and special technologies for teaching English (Define It, Drawing Distance (Playful Pictures), Run to the Board, Memory Story, Board Race, Pistuanary Race, Lip Reading, Opinion/Running Distances, Word by Word Story, Sleep and Wake Up), diagnosing the implementation of knowledge in practice using exercises and mutimedial educational programs, showing how necessary it is to follow them in everyday life forms the main basis of the content of the curriculum.

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